

LIVING FROM THE DISTANCE: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Living far from the school is a clear picture of the challenges students face in their educational journey. This study investigated the lived experiences of students studying at sto Niño High School, Tanjay City Division, who reside in far areas from the school, for the school year 2023-2024. The study utilized a phenomenology design to describe and understand the situation of the participants. Focused group discussion was employed by the researcher through a trained teacher to collect the data for reflexivity purposes. Moreover, a consented audio recording was a big help for transcribing the participants' verbatim responses then were analyzed through thematic analysis. This entailed the researcher familiarizing the transcripts, generating codes, combining codes into themes, reviewing themes, defining themes, and reporting the findings. The result revealed six themes that shed light on the experiences of the participants including inconvenience, emotional distress, less socialization, low academic performance, financial constraints, and resourcefulness and resiliency. These results will be disseminated to the schools in Tanjay City division especially to hinterland schools and will be the basis for teachers' action plans and school program initiatives. Thus, the study recommends that teachers be observant of the situation of their learners and help them by any possible means that could aid their education. Furthermore, this study also suggests that schools should tap into community stakeholders for better implementation of the school's initiatives.

Keywords: *Phenomenology, lived experiences among students residing far from school, Tanjay City Division, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

Regardless of where they live, all people should have access to education as it is a fundamental right. However, many people still live in remote places and find it difficult to obtain education. These individuals usually have unique life experiences that impact their academic careers. However, living in a rural location presents several obstacles for students. This includes limited access to resources, transportation and distance, financial hardships, and social and emotional well-being.

Limited access to resources can seriously impair a student's capacity for academic success and have an ongoing negative impact on their educational outcomes. These students are unable to access reading materials, technology-based learning, or educational facilities available if they reside in urban areas. This situation has led students to not enjoy their performance in their subjects (Gaotlhobogwe, 2021). In addition, Internet accessibility hinders learners' participation in the educational process. Nowadays, teachers employ strategies and pedagogies that have proven effective in making the teaching process more efficient and effective. The integration of research principles by sourcing information and data through varied academic sources has been included in the curriculum to maximize students' and teachers' critical and problem-solving skills. However, the situation of students living in remote areas hinders their performance in activities that require academic research. This could affect motivation, self-efficacy, learning, mood, and emotions (HeinOnline, 2024). In this high regard, teachers play an important role in providing support for these deprived learners. They can give students reading materials, workbooks, printed worksheets, and textbooks for use at home as offline learning resources. Verify that these materials offer precise directions for self-guided learning and are in line with the curriculum (Staff, 2023). In addition, aside from giving parallel activities and handouts, teachers can diversify tasks and projects regardless of the type of learners they have. By giving them opportunities and freedom to choose what approach to do their assignments, all the learners will be able to show their skills and knowledge despite internet inconvenience (Cchiaro, 2020).

Moreover, the students' experiences did not stop there. Owing to the absence of a vehicle, students find it challenging to navigate from their houses to school. Regular school commutes are difficult for students to complete because of insufficient infrastructure, including roads and transportation. To get to school, they must walk for an hour or more to demonstrate their commitment to study despite the difficulties posed by their isolated location. Learners who must go a considerable distance every day from their house to school spend less time sleeping and studying, which causes them to wake up late (Zuckerman, D. (2021). Early Morning Classes, Sleepy Students, and Risky Behaviors. - References - Scientific Research Publishing, n.d.). This can affect their emotional state whenever these learners arrive at school, they tend to be tired and exhibit less understanding and less interaction in class discussions which sometimes results in sleep mode. In this scenario, teachers naturally wake up students from sleeping and persuade them to listen and participate in the class. However, this affects the student's emotional well-being. The less sleep people get, the less social interaction they desire.

Consequently, they become more socially unappealing to others, which exacerbates the serious social isolation effects of sleep deprivation, this cycle could be a major contributing factor to the loneliness public health crisis (How Poor Sleep Can Ruin Your Social Life, 2018). Relatively, according to Peteros et al. (2022), this is true since learning is naturally affected by inner and outer stimuli. These circumstances adversely affect the student's education. Students who are living in remote areas have lower levels of social, emotional, and academic well-being (Duckworth et al., n.d.) Moreover, financial constraints hinder the learners from acquiring materials and accessing devices that can be of great contribution to their education. This scenario can be attributed to parents who have less income and who just make things enough to meet the necessities to survive daily living. In this situation, parents prioritize food and shelter, although sometimes not enough, rather than providing materials and school supplies for their learners. Thus, financial constraints affect student academic performance (KUPTM, n.d.). This phenomenon is related to the study titled, Effects of Distance to School and Poverty on Learners' Academic Performance in Four Selected Rural Primary Schools in Chibombo District of Central Province. Based on the results, it is found that learners' academic performance is negatively impacted by poverty and travel time to school. According to the report, the Ministry of Education should work with the government to build additional elementary schools in rural areas and support school food programs for vulnerable children living in these areas (Chitondo, 2022).

There are numerous challenges that students face when residing in far-flung and remote areas from the school where they enroll. A relevant study titled, The Effects of school distance on Students' Academic Performance: A Case of Community Secondary Schools in Makambako Town Council presented those students who commuted farther to school arrived at their destinations later in the day and with empty stomachs. The location of the school has contributed to mass failure for most students, as long walks have resulted in dropout rates and a high percentage of pregnant girls, who are unable to complete their education. Community secondary schools in Makambako Town Council will continue to perform poorly academically if efforts are not made to improve the quality of education provided to these schools (Mhiliwa, 2015).

As mentioned above, distance and transportation, scantiness of educational resources, and financial problems are common gaps students face. These difficulties may significantly affect their general academic performance and personal growth. Students who attend school in remote locations frequently have restricted access to experiences, resources, and support networks easily accessible to their peers in populous or urban areas. This might result from feelings of loneliness, isolation, and a lack of ties to peers and communities. Consequently, these issues may create psychological distress in learners. According to a recent University of Houston study, although people may connect remote locations with tranquil scenery and quiet lifestyles, rural residents face higher rates of anxiety and depression than their urban counterparts (*Health Research Institute Rural Residents Are More Depressed and Anxious Than Those in Urban Areas, UH Study Finds*, 2023).

The experiences of students who live far from their school pose a threat to their future if not understood and taken considerably. In this regard, to understand this phenomenon better, the researcher proposes this investigation of the situation of some students at Sto Niño High School who live in the far-flung areas in Barangay Sto Niño, a hinterland place in Tanjay City, Negros Oriental in the academic year 2023-2024. Thus, the result of the study will be the basis for the school's improvement plan highlighting the support of these learners.

Research Questions

This study investigates the lived experiences of students at Sto Niño High School, Tanjay City in the academic year 2023-2024. Thus, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What are the lived experiences of students who are studying at Sto Niño High School?
2. What is the meaning of their experiences?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a phenomenological approach to investigate the lived experiences of the students living in far-flung areas in Barangay Sto. Niño where the school is in the academic year 2023-2024. The researcher employed purposive sampling since the participants of this study were qualified based on the criteria for pre-selection of the participants. These include the distance and hours spent going to school and vice versa. The distance of their residences is 4-6 kilometers and it takes them to walk for an hour or more since there are no vehicles available in their respective places. Furthermore, the researcher had twelve (12) prospected participants. Six (6) of these participants were initially interviewed for pilot testing. With consented audio recording and transcription, the data was saturated which led the researcher to commence the actual data gathering of the six (6) remaining students through Focused Group Discussion (FGD).

To analyze the data, the researcher utilized Braun and Clarke's thematic analysis. Moreover, to confirm that the researcher's interpretations accurately reflected the participants' intended meaning, member checking was also conducted. Furthermore, the degree of confirmability enhances the study's credibility. This criterion, confirmability, measures how much the research study's conclusions are based on the participants' accounts and assertions rather than likely researcher biases (Moran, 2021). In this high regard, the researcher used reflexivity to preserve the study's objectivity. Here, the researcher chose a trained teacher to lead the concentrated group discussion with the participants.

RESULTS

Table 1. Thematic Map

Codes	Themes
Far distance No vehicle to be used going to school and vice versa No cellphone, weak signal, and no internet access Walking under the rain and heat of the sun	Inconvenience
Walking alone most of the time going home and vice versa Afraid of what will happen along the way Feels sad whenever come late to class Feels frustrated whenever cannot research for assignments	Emotional distress
Isolated sometimes Limited interaction with classmates, schoolmates, and teachers Cannot join clubs and organizations Cannot attend to group tasks	Less socialization
Dried fish and rice for lunch only No money was given from the parents Parents' work is farming Less income to sustain daily needs	Financial constraint
Less participation in the classroom Low grades in most of the subject areas	Low academic performance
Root crops as their snack Banana leaves as an alternative during heavy rains and the hotness of the day Using plastic as an alternative bag for their materials during heavy rains Walking with their bare feet just to go to school	Resourcefulness and resiliency

DISCUSSION

This section encapsulates the overall result of the research. Through thematic analysis, codes and themes were generated to highlight the lived experiences of the students who live in the remote areas of Barangay Sto. Niño, Tanjay City. This thematic analysis is employed to delve deep into the personal experiences of students in their education in remote areas of the said Barangay. By using thematic analysis, the researcher gained a comprehensive understanding of the unique experiences and challenges of these students as they navigate from their respective homes to school.

Inconvenience

Living in far distant areas can pose challenges for students especially when it comes to receiving a quality education. These challenges range from difficulties commuting to school to accessing learning materials. Students in regions often encounter inconveniences that their urban or suburban counterparts may not face. Those residing in areas experience obstacles, such as limited educational resources, lack of transportation, and difficulties dealing with academics. The theme of inconvenience is supported by the responses of participants.

Participant 1 said,

“Layu kaayu amu sir. Maglisud jud ko sir kai wala may mi magamit na sakyanan or motor ba para mahatod m sir so maglakaw nalang ko sir sag maglisud ko sa dalan labi najud ug danlog. Dayun paita kaayu sir kai wala mi diri wifi nya wala kaayu signal. So, dili mi maka research”.

“Our house is far from the school sir. I found it difficult since we don’t have vehicles to be used going to school and vice versa. For this reason, I just walk every day no matter how hard sometimes deal with slippery roads and pathways. Moreover, it is difficult on my end since we don’t have internet access in our place which makes it hard for us to research”.

Moreover, participant 3 answered,

“Ako pud sir. Hapit duha ka oras ko maglakaw kay wala jud mi magamit na motor para adto eskwelahan. Tinuod pud na sir na maglisud mi sa among mga assignments kai dili mi ka research kai wala mi internet. Usahay mangayu nalang mi sa among teachers ug handouts para basahon kai wala pud mi cellphone para maka research.”

“Me too sir. I walk every day for almost two hours going to school and vice versa since we don’t have a vehicle. It is indeed difficult for us to do our assignments since we don’t have an internet connection in our place. Sometimes, due to the absence of devices like cellphones, we just ask our teachers to give us handouts for us to review and do our tasks.”

Participants 1 and 3 strongly emphasized how hard it is for them to deal with going to school and vice versa. The long hours of walk and the absence of vehicles as means of transportation, make their lives as students more challenging. Moreover, the inaccessibility of resources and devices also adversely affects their education. They cannot do some tasks that require further research or internet connectivity since they do not have cell phones or Wi-Fi in their area.

Emotional Distress

One of the challenges for students in remote areas is the emotional distress that they feel as a result of living from a distance. Having no vehicle leads them no choice but to walk and deal with possible things along the way. Also, students who live in far-flung places may face particular difficulties that result in greater rates of emotional distress. These people do not have the same access to opportunities and resources as their counterparts in cities. Among other mental health problems, this isolation can cause feelings of loneliness, worry, and sadness. Participants' responses supported this statement.

Participant 4 said,

“Mag inusara rako ug lakaw sir padulong sa eskwelahan ug pagpauli pud sa balay. Mao ng kuyawan ko sir. Dili gyud lalim. Ma late pud ko ug makaguol kai usahay maulahi q ug naai test or quiz among teacher sir. Dayun, wala pud koi selpon sir hinungdan nga dili ko makagama ug assignments mao ng hatagan ko sa akong teachers ug mga balasahun para naa ko basehan sa akong answers.”

“I just walk alone sir going to school and vice versa and that makes me feel nervous and worried. It's not easy on my part. I even come to school late, which frustrates me because there are quizzes and tests that I miss sometimes. In addition, I do not have a cellphone, which hinders me from completing assignments. My teacher just gives me handouts for me to read and make it the basis for my answers.”

Moreover, Participant 6 added,

“Ako pud sir. Ma late jud ko kai mupahuway pa man pud ko ang hapit baya 2 ka oras akong lakaw sir paingun sa school ug pagpauli. Makuyawan gani ko maglakaw usahay sir kai ako ragud usa. Usahay, muhapit ko sa akong kaila na estudyanti harun magkuyog mi sir peru mga 45 minuto pa una ko maabot sa ilaha. Usahay gani kai maulahi nako sa test namu sir and sayangan ko kai magtuon baya pud ko sa balay sir.”

“Me too sir. I am late for school because I still need to rest. I had to walk for almost two hours, going to school and going home. In this regard, I felt worried and nervous, knowing that I was alone. In addition, I stopped by at my schoolmate's house, so we could go together at school sometimes. However, it took 45 minutes

before I arrived at their house. I also felt sad when I was late for our tests and quizzes especially since I studied at home.”

Individuals' futures are greatly shaped by their education, which equips them with the knowledge and abilities needed to thrive in life. However, as they negotiate the difficulties and demands that come with the quest for academic greatness, students frequently experience worries and sad emotions during their educational journey. In this statement, participants 4 and 6 expressed their emotions highlighting worries and sadness caused by living far from their school.

Less Socialization

Students' sociability is significantly impacted by living distant from campus. The ability to socialize has become crucial to the student's experience in today's connected world. Through social interactions on campus, students can create lifelong friendships and professional ties. However, socialization possibilities are limited for students who reside distant from campus. The physical separation between learners and their peers is one of the primary causes of this lack of socializing. It was difficult for students to attend social gatherings, club meetings, and other school events if they resided far away. This separation can make it difficult for them to get to know one another and can lead to feelings of loneliness and isolation. Thus, this statement is supported by the responses of participants 2 and 5.

Participant 2 said,

“Mao lage pud sir kai tungod nga layu amu, di nako makaapil ug mga club and organizations sa school kai ug naai mga panagtapok kai di japon ko kaapil kai layu man amua. Need ko musayu. Masuya ko usahay sir nga mag inusara sa kilid. Dayun ug naai mga activities sa school kai di japon ko maka enjoy kaayu kai need ko mouli dayun sir magabin.an napud ko.”

“I cannot join school clubs and organizations Sir. I cannot join if there are meetings since our house is far away. I needed to go home early so I would not come home late. Then, if there are activities in school, I cannot enjoy as much as I love to that is why I feel jealous, alone, and isolated. It is really hard for me to interact and socialize with my classmates and teachers with that matter.”

In addition, Participant 5 answered,

“Tinuod na sir. Makasuya baya kai ang uban nga estudyanti kai makaparticipate sila ug naai mga activities while ako di jud. Ganahan unta ko muapil peru di ko ka buhat sa uban nga responsibilidad kai pag naai meeting, di ko ka apil kai kailangan ko musayu uli. Panalgasa rapud ko makaapil ug mga activities sa school sir nya ug maka higayun pud ko, di pud ko maka pagusto ug enjoy kauban sa akong mga classmates, ug mga maestra ug maestro. Imbes nga maka palami ug istorya dili nalang kai maghuna huna ko na magabin.an ko mauli.”

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“That is true sir. I felt jealous because other students could participate in school activities while I could not. I wanted to join but I could not because of the responsibilities I may not be able to fulfill. If there are meetings about it, I could not just attend since I need to go home early. Although so often that I could join activities in school, I could not enjoy interacting and enjoying the moment with my classmates and teachers because I had to go home early.”

Being situated in a far-flung area tremendously affects the sociability of learners. Thus, this is emphasized by participants 2 and 5 when they said that living far from the school limited their opportunities for socialization and interaction.

Financial Constraint

Parents play a significant role in the learners' education. To guarantee that they have access to a high-quality education, parents' financial support is essential. However, if parents do not have an adequate source of income, the learners' education is affected. In this theme, it is evident that students experienced difficulties and challenges in their journey to education in terms of their necessities and access to other resources that are pertinent to their studies. Having no food for snacks and water makes them endure what their parents can afford. This concept is explained by the experiences of the participants.

Participant 1 said,

“Di man ko tagaan ug balon sa akong mga ginikanan sir kai wala man silay kwarta. Mang uuma ra pareho akong ginikanan nya gamay ra ug sweldo. Igu rajud makakaon ika tulo sa usa ka adlaw. Mag sud.an ra gani mi ug bulad dayun kan.on. kasagaran kan.on rajd ug patis amu sud.an ug mao rapd ako balunon sa eskwelahan pag pa niudto.”

“My parents do not give me money because they do not have enough. My parents are both farmers and their income is only enough for a three times a day meal. Dried fish and rice are what we ate for our meals. Most of the time, I just eat rice and soy sauce for my lunch.”

In addition, Participant 5 said,

“Ang trabaho sa akong mga ginikanan sir kai mang uuma raman mao ng gamay ra sila ug sweldo. Dili pud maka hatag nako ug kwarta silang mama kai igu rajud ang ilaha sweldo sa among pang adlaw adlaw. Usahay kulanganon gani sir. Usahay mutabang ko ila ug pang uma haron naai mapuno gamay sa amu panginahanglan sir.”

“Both of my parents are farmers, and their income is just enough for our daily basis. Sometimes, not enough for all our needs. Moreover, they could not

give me money which made me help them farm to earn and contribute to the family's daily needs."

Money is indeed a catalyst to make things work. In education, it plays a crucial role in financing all the needs of the students yet a constraint of it tremendously resulted in challenges encountered and endured among students who experienced the phenomenon. Participants 1 and 5 faced these challenges without complaining instead, understood the situation and even made an effort to help the family's situation.

Low academic performance

The goal of education is for learners to discover their learning styles and to receive passing marks for their hard work and sacrifices. The sense of completion they get from finishing a course or set of subjects has a favorable effect on their well-being and positive outlook on life. However, because of underlying issues like living far from the school, it can be difficult for them to handle the difficulties that attending school may present. In this case, the participants in this study revealed that they walked long hours to reach the school since there was no vehicle available in their situation. As a result, they felt tired and did not have the energy to participate in class discussions. Moreover, they got low scores on their quizzes and exams. This situation can be noticed in the participants' words.

Participant 3 said,

"Tungod sa kakapoy sa akong paglakaw sir kai mawad.an nako ug gana nga maminaw pag. abot sa eskwelahan. Katulugon nako sir. Mao ng ug mag test si maam kai gagmay ko ug kuha. Usahay gani kai Kasab,an ko sa akong maestra kai nganu daw sige ko katulugon sa klase mao tong nakasabot rapud sila then padad.an ko nila ug balasahon."

"I felt exhausted when arrived at school which made me lose my interest in listening and participating in class activities. I just felt sleepy. Whenever our teachers conducted a test, I always got low scores. Our teacher asked me why I was always sleepy in class, so I told them of my situation and then they understood and helped me. They gave me some handouts to read at home".

Participant 6 added,

"Ako pud sir. Nasultian pud ko sa akong mga teachers nganu sige ko katulugon sa klase ug ni ingun pud ko na layu amu. Na alarma daw sila kai gagmay kaayu ko ug kuha sa mga test namu nya dili pud daw ko tig participate kaayu sir. Sukad eto, tagaan pud ko ug mga handouts sa among teachers para naa daw ko katun an".

“Me too Sir. My teachers also asked me why I was always sleepy in class. They were alarmed by my low scores obtained from the tests and added that I was not participating in class activities. For that, I told them my situation and they understood it. They even gave me handouts so that there is something I can read at home”.

In general, a student's academic performance can be greatly impacted by the distance between their home and school. Students who live far away from home have several obstacles to overcome that can hinder their academic performance, such as trouble getting about, fewer extracurricular activities available to them, and higher stress levels. Participants 3 and 6 highlighted their experiences about how tired and unmotivated they were when they arrived at school from walking a long distance. Due to this, their academic performance is adversely affected. On the other hand, teachers' care and concern are evident when it was expressed by the participants that their teachers asked them about the possible causes of their behavior in the classroom. Thus, their teachers give them handouts for something to be read at home.

Resourcefulness and resiliency

Learning can be hard sometimes. Due to many reasons that may contribute to the student's success or failure in their education, some may endure, and some may just stop. In this case, the situation of the participants in this study is a vivid manifestation that living far from the school naturally challenged them to decide for themselves whether to continue or stop their education. Although, this has made them a lot of sacrifices, but their conviction to pursue their education can be described as commendable. In this theme, the participants shared their practices reflecting on being resourceful and resilient despite the hardships they needed to face in their education.

Participant 2 said,

“ Walay mahatag nga kwarta akong ginikanan para snack sir mao ng mangalot nalang ko ug kamote then manguha pud ko ug ginangmay nga saging dayun aqng lung.agon dayun mao akong balunon sa skwelahan sir. Dayun, ug mag ulan sir kai manguha lang ko ug dahun sa saging maoy akong himuon na payong. Then, syempre ug mag yutik jud ang dalan, mag tiniil rako dayun manghinaw rako pag abot sa among school. Mao gani mg problema ko usahay ug mag.ulan sir kay akong bag guba na. wala nai tarong nga zipper. Mao ng mangayu nalang ko ug plastic sa mga tindahan sa proper sir didto nako isulod ang akong notebook ug ktong gipanghatag nila maam ug sir nga mga handouts. Sag maglisud ko, peru gi agwanta ra nako sir kai ganahn ko makapadayun ug makatiwas ug ewkwela”.

“My parents do not give me money for snacks sir that is why I just harvest some sweet potatoes in our backyard and get some bananas and cook these all together for my snacks. In terms of rainy days, I also get banana leaves as a cover

for my head since we cannot afford to buy an umbrella. Also, I have a problem with my bag since it is almost broken, and the zipper is not working. In this regard, I just asked for a plastic bag from the stores and put my things including my notebooks and the handouts that were given by my teachers. I know it's really hard for me, but I have to endure and find ways to continue and finish my studies”.

Moreover, participant 4 answered,

“Ako pud sir. Manguha rapud ko ug dahon sa saging akong ipandong bastag init or ulan ba. Magbalon rapud ko ug plastic sir kai aq rapud isulod ang akong mga gamit. Mag tiniil rapud ko sir nya magbalon rako ug tsinelas dayun adto rako manghinaw sa eskwelahan. Wala koy sapatos kai dili maka palit akong mga ginikanan. Dili gani sila makahatag nako ug kwarta para balon. Mao ng harun dili ko gutumon sa eskwelahan, mangita ko ug mag salag.on nga ako malung.ag ug akong mabalon. Ou, lisud among kahimtang sir, peru akong gikaya kai ganahn ko makatiwas ug eskwela sir harun makatabang ko sa akong pamilya puhon”.

“Same here sir. I just get banana leaves to cover myself when it's too hot and when raining. I just secured a plastic bag and put my things in it whenever rain occurs. I just walk with my barefoot, and I just carry my slippers and just clean up when I arrive at school. I don't have shoes too. My parents cannot afford to buy me one. They can't even give me money for my allowance which is why I just look for any root crops that I can cook so there is something I can eat for my snack at school. Yes, my situation indeed seems to be challenging but I just have to deal with it. I have to endure everything and find ways to overcome whatever hurdles hinder my way. I have to be strong so I can finish my studies and be able to help my family in the future”.

Challenges are said to be the counterpart of the ladder of success. Enduring and staying focused to continue their studies are what participants 2 and 4 emphasized. Despite the difficulties they encountered, they demonstrated resourcefulness and resiliency that made them stronger in life, especially in their education journey. With these values, the participants even made clear that whatever hurdles their way, they will still strive for themselves and their family's future.

Conclusions

The study concluded that the lived experiences of the students who live far from their school highlighted the challenges and effects on their academic performance and emotional and social well-being. Moreover, resourcefulness and resiliency were found to be a strong will for these students to keep focused on their goals to continue and finish their studies.

Living far from the school posed several challenges to the participants. One of these is the inconvenience that they experience in their daily journey. This is evident by the absence of vehicles which led them to come late to school, the absence of gadgets like cellphones, weak signals, and no internet access which resulted in low academic performance. Having no cellphones or any means of online surfing prevents these learners from doing extra research for their assignments and projects and makes them feel frustrated. In this regard, teachers showed understanding of the student's situation and provided them with materials they could read at home. This study also revealed that living far from the school hinders the participants from exercising their social skills. They prefer not to join school clubs and organizations because they worry much if they cannot fulfill their responsibilities since it is hard in their situation. Furthermore, parents' financial constraints also contributed to students' challenges. Learners were deprived of basic needs since their parents' jobs were farming and the family's income was only enough for a daily basis. This explains why the participants understood and kept enduring what their situation might bring to their everyday lives including their education.

Living far from the school presents a regular problem for a lot of students worldwide. In this study, several problems were faced by the participants including transportation, motivation toward academic stance, limited emotional and social expression, and connection. However, participants showed incredible will in enduring their daily experiences. These students demonstrated resourcefulness and resiliency to parallel the challenges in their situation. They continue to go to school no matter how far it would take them only by walking with their bare feet and in times of rainy and sunny days, they use banana leaves as an alternative to cover their bodies. Also, they ask for plastic bags from stores they could pass by to save their materials from getting wet since their bag is no longer in good condition. Their determination does not stop there. Participants learned to find ways to look for something that will serve as their snack in school since their parents do not give them an allowance. Bringing cooked root crops such as sweet potato and banana from their backyard is what saved them as their snacks.

Learners who reside far from school have certain difficulties that can make it challenging for them to travel to class every day. But when they figure out how to get beyond these challenges and carry on with their schooling, their resourcefulness and fortitude come through. These students show a genuine commitment to their education and a strong belief in the ability of learning to improve their lives, whether it be through using transportation, coming up with alternative ways, or just making the effort to get to school every day.

Recommendations

Based on the results of the study, the researcher reminds teachers to be more observant of their students' situation so they can provide any means of support to survive their education. Moreover, it is important to practice community linkages to better implement any program that will benefit the learners and the school. Research-wise, future researchers may include urban schools since the present study focused on only one school in the hinterland to elicit more experiences and differences in their situations.

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Also, the pragmatic method can be applied too. Combining both qualitative and quantitative can have a tremendous impact on studies like this.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

I, Mr. Joseph Torres, author of this study hereby declare that the implementation of the study took a careful and ethical approach. Before the actual implementation of the study, the researcher sent a permission letter to the school's division office for approval. After being approved, the researcher invited the possible participants for an orientation. The agenda included the nature and the purpose of the study, informed consent, the anonymity of the participants, the confidentiality of the data, and the freedom to withdraw. All of these were explained well and understood by the would-be participants. Consequently, the participants gave their support and signed the informed consent. Furthermore, the study is not plagiarized, and the sources cited in this paper are properly acknowledged. Also, to avoid bias, the researcher trained a teacher to collect the data through focused group discussion.

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